

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

ASSESSMENT OF DENTISTS' SELF-REPORTED LEVELS OF INCOME AND BURNOUT DIMENSIONS: A PRELIMINARY INVESTIGATION

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this preliminary investigation was to assess dental professionals' income satisfaction and its related levels of burnout dimensions: EE, DP, and PA. An anonymous descriptive cross-sectional survey was held among 156 dentists working in the capital of Republic of Bulgaria, Sofia. The questionnaire consisted of demographic data and the Maslach Burnout Inventory-Human Services Survey (MBI-HSS) sections. A total of 136 dentists provided duly completed questionnaires (RR = 90.7%), of which 56 (41.2%) were males. Surprisingly, almost a quarter – 32 (23.5%), reported having unsatisfactory income from dentistry contrary to the notion that this occupation was considered well paid and providing security in this regard. This group of dentists demonstrated higher levels of burnout than those with good or excellent income. They exhibited higher scores mainly in EE and reduced PA subscales. Therefore, recommendations for positive outcomes of dental procedures which are crucial for patient well-being and satisfaction, might have a key role in evaluation of achieved results, including their financial aspect. Ultimately, better compensation, motivation and performance could effectively help reduce the risk of burnout.

Keywords: dentists, dentistry, burnout, income satisfaction, MBI-HSS.

Introduction

One of the most widely used definitions of burnout given by Maslach and Jackson determines burnout as a syndrome of emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and a feeling of dissatisfaction with self-realization [1-3]. Emotional exhaustion (EE) refers to depletion of emotional resources caused by the presence of conflicts of a different nature – internal, interpersonal, etc. Depersonalization (DP) refers to development of a negative, heartless and cynical attitude towards service recipients. The term depersonalization can cause some confusion because it is used in psychiatry to refer to extreme alienation from oneself and the world. However, in Maslach and Jackson's definition, depersonalization refers to an impersonal and dehumanizing treatment of recipients rather than oneself. Finally, the failure to achieve the desired personal realization gives rise to a tendency to evaluate the work with the recipients as negative. Thus, among "burned out" professionals, the feeling of unachieved goals is accompanied by low professional self-esteem [2,4].

Regarding dentistry, a very well-documented fact has been the association of burnout and career satisfaction rates with dental professionals' quality of life and respectively, the quality of dental services provided [5]. In this aspect, studies focusing on evaluation of burnout predictors might be of great significance for both dentists' and patients' physical and psychological well-being. Multiple lines of evidence have suggested a positive relationship between chronic occupational distress and burnout levels [6-8]. Zhang et al. reported that factors associated with psychological distress for dentists were lower income, career-choice regret, lack of sufficient personal time, etc. [9]. According to Wasoski economic factors such as the cost of a dental education or the start-up costs of a practice might be significant stressors if not considered as a career investment [8]. Cigerim et al. found that monthly income was inversely

associated with depression [10]. Therefore, ensuring adequate and equitable financial income could be identified as an effective strategy for affecting job motivation, career satisfaction, and burnout levels [5,11].

The aim of this preliminary investigation on burnout rates among Bulgarian dentists was to assess dental professionals' income satisfaction and its related levels of burnout dimensions: EE, DP, and PA.

Material and methods

An anonymous descriptive cross-sectional survey was held among 156 dentists working in the capital of Republic of Bulgaria, Sofia. Inclusion criteria for all study participants were: 1) to be dentists with least one-year practical experience; 2) to be working in individual or group practices for primary or specialized dental care, dental or medical and dental centers; 3) to be voluntary consent to take part in the present study.

Questionnaires were administered at the dental offices of the participants and the latter were not offered any additional incentives or rewards for taking part in the study. Dentists were informed about the purpose of the study, the methods used, and were given precise instructions prior to filling out the surveys. Additionally, they were kindly asked to answer all questions anonymously and honestly. Respondents were assured that their anonymity and data confidentiality would be preserved. Voluntary completion of the questionnaire was accepted as a form of individual written informed consent to participate in the study. Furthermore, the latter was conducted in full accordance with the ethical standards of the Ethics research committee at the MU-Sofia and the WMA Declaration of Helsinki as revised in 2013.

The main research instrument consisted of two parts: 1. Socio-demographic profile and characteristics of the workplace; 2. Standard burnout research methodology, through the Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI-HSS; Maslach & Jackson, 1996). The first part

contained 20 questions, grouped into three sections, related to collecting information on dentists' socio-demographic characteristics, working environment factors, dentists' self-assessment about the income received from the dental practice, the presence of activities not related to work (hobbies or side interests); presence of unhealthy stereotypes related to lifestyle (smoking, alcohol abuse, sedative medications, antidepressants or sleeping pills, as well as insomnia) and issues related to professional planning and the desire to work after retirement. The questions were close ended, some of them with an option to specify more than one answer. The second part of the questionnaire contained 22 statements to measure the three aspects of burnout – emotional exhaustion – EE (nine items); depersonalization – DP (five items) and personal accomplishment – PA (eight items). Answers to the questions in the three subscales of the MBI-HSS were assessed on a seven-point Likert scale with codes from 0 to 6: 0 – no, never; 1 – very rare; 2 – rarely; 3 – sometimes; 4 – often; 5 – very often; 6 – always (Maslach & Jackson, 1986) [12]. The Bulgarian translation of the questionnaire was validated

and used by medical personnel in Bulgaria by B. Tsenova (1991, 2002, 2004) [13]. The internal consistency reliability of the entire questionnaire was good – 0.757. For the EE, DP and PA subscales, it was 0.926, 0.726 and 0.816, respectively [14]. Finally, dentists' self-reported level of income was assessed by using a 3-point scale: excellent, good and unsatisfactory.

Data were processed with the statistical package IBM SPSS Statistics v.25.0. Standard descriptive statistics was used to present demographic data of the study sample as well as the levels of EE, DP and PA in the context of respondents' self-perceived level of income. Results were presented as frequency distributions (number, percentage).

Results and discussion

A total of 156 questionnaires were initially distributed, 5 were excluded as more of the questions were left unanswered, 1 dentist refused to participate. Subsequently, there were left 150 surveys, of which 136 were duly completed (RR = 90.7%). Of these, 56 (41.2%) were males and 80 (58.8%) were females. Further demographic data of the sample can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1

Demographic characteristics of the study sample (n=136)

Variables	N	%
Age		
25-40 years	32	23.5
41-55 years	72	53.0
56+	32	23.5
Gender		
Male	56	41.2
Female	80	58.8
Years in practice		
Up to 15 years	48	35.3
16-30 years	56	41.2
30+ years	32	23.5
Type of dental practice		
Individual	80	58.8
Group	56	41.2
Ownership of dental office		
Own dental office	80	58.8
Rented dental office	40	29.4
Own + rented dental office	16	11.8

In this study dentists' self-assessment regarding the amount of their income from dental practice was investigated by using a three-point scale – excellent, good and unsatisfactory. The results suggested that more than half of the respondents – 72 (53%) – defined their income from the dental practice as good. Almost a quarter – 32 (23.5%) indicated that they had very good (excellent) income. However, the remaining one quarter of respondents – 32 (23.5%), reported having unsatisfactory income from dentistry contrary to the notion

that this occupation was considered well paid and providing security in this regard.

When analyzing burnout dimensions and levels of income, data revealed that in the group of dentists with very good and good income, moderate and low levels of emotional exhaustion prevailed while high levels of EE were more prevalent among dentists with unsatisfactory income (table 2).

Table 2

Frequency distribution of dentists by income and emotional exhaustion (EE)

EE \ Income	Low level (n, %)	Moderate level (n, %)	High level (n, %)	Very high level (n, %)	Total (n, %)
Excellent	8(14.3%)	16(50%)	8(25%)	0(0%)	32(23.5%)
Good	32(57.1%)	16(50%)	8(25%)	16(100%)	72(53%)
Unsatisfactory	16(28,6%)	0(0%)	16(50%)	0(0%)	32(23.5%)
Total (n, %)	56(100%)	32(100%)	32(100%)	16(100%)	136(100%)

Regarding depersonalization subscale, we found that respondents with good income predominantly demonstrated moderate levels of DP. There were no prevailing trends among the other two groups of examined subjects with respect to this dimension of burnout (Table 3). Finally, assessment of data concerning the third aspect of burnout syndrome showed that dentists

having excellent and good levels of self-reported income mainly exhibited moderate level of reduced personal accomplishment (PA). High level of reduced PA was primarily registered in the group of dentists that reported having unsatisfactory income from dentistry (Table 4).

Table 3

Frequency distribution of dentists by income and depersonalization (DP)

DP \ Income	Low level (n, %)	Moderate level (n, %)	High level (n, %)	Very high level (n, %)	Total (n, %)
Excellent	8(33.3%)	8(16.7%)	8(33.3%)	8(20%)	32(23.5%)
Good	8(33.3%)	32(66.6%)	8(33.3%)	24(60%)	72(53%)
Unsatisfactory	8(33.3%)	8(16.7%)	8(33.3%)	8(20%)	32(23.5%)
Total (n, %)	24(100%)	48(100%)	24(100%)	40(100%)	136(100%)

Table 4

Frequency distribution of dentists by income and personal accomplishment (PA)

Reduced PA \ Income	Low level (n, %)	Moderate level (n, %)	High level (n, %)	Very high level (n, %)	Total (n, %)
Excellent	8(25%)	16(28.6%)	0(0%)	8(50%)	32(23.5%)
Good	16(50%)	40(71.4%)	16(50%)	0(0%)	72(53%)
Unsatisfactory	8(25%)	0(0%)	16(50%)	8(50%)	32(23.5%)
Total (n, %)	32(100%)	56(100%)	32(100%)	16(100%)	136(100%)

Conclusion

Dentists that reported having unsatisfactory income from their dental practice demonstrated higher levels of burnout than those with good or excellent income. They exhibited higher scores mainly in EE and reduced PA subscales. Therefore, recommendations for positive outcomes of dental procedures which are crucial for patient well-being and satisfaction, might have a key role in evaluation of achieved results, including their financial aspect. Ultimately, better compensation, motivation and performance could effectively help reduce the risk of burnout.

Statement of conflict of interest

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest with this research article.

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